

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-50-IC-5% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	21	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 50
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/29/2022 17:10:07 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 19:48:04 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.460	3367870	50.19	347493
2	7.059	3342962	49.81	307374

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-56-IC-5% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	20221031
Vial:	12	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 56
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/31/2022 11:36:36 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 19:47:50 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.306	270383	3.02	20055
2	6.869	8680748	96.98	756651